

A STUDY ON STOCK MARKET WITH REFERENCE TO INDIAN ECONOMY**Mr. Sajith.M**

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ABSTRACT

The stock market plays a significant role in the development of the economic system of a country. The objective of the present study, i.e., "A Study on Stock Market with Reference to the Indian Economy," is to study the level of awareness and participation of individuals in the stock market. The study aims to identify how the factors of age, gender, and educational qualifications influence the individuals.

The study is based on primary research, which is carried out with the help of a structured questionnaire survey of 61 respondents. Various statistical methods are used for analysing the research data. These methods include percentage analysis, descriptive statistics, Independent Sample T-Test, and One-Way ANOVA. The findings of the research reveal that the majority of the people are aware of the concept of stock market investment. However, the willingness to participate in the stock market investment is based on several factors. These factors are education, knowledge, and risk. It is also revealed that financial literacy plays a key role in motivating people to participate in the stock market.

The research concludes that awareness and financial literacy may play an important role in motivating people to participate in the stock market. This will help in the development of the Indian stock market and the Indian economy.

INTRODUCTION

The stock market has an important role in the development of any country's economy, and that is the mobilization and proper utilization of savings. It can be defined as an marketplace between those who have surplus funds and those who need funds for growth and development. In emerging economies like India, the stock market has acquired significant importance due to economic liberalization, technological advancements, and increased investor participation.

Stock market can be defined as an arena where securities like shares, debentures, bonds, and derivatives are traded. It provides liquidity, facilitates price discovery, and mirrors the economical progress of any nation in the world. The emergence of stock exchanges like Bombay Stock Exchange and National Stock Exchange has revolutionized the financial system in India.

Over the past few decades, India's stock market has shown remarkable growth in terms of market capitalization, trading volume, and retail investor participation. The government's initiatives, financial sector reforms, and supervision by the Securities Exchange Board of India have helped boost investor confidence. In addition, the availability of digital trading platforms and mobile apps has helped more young investors participate in the stock market.

Problem Description

The stock market plays a crucial role in mobilizing savings and supporting economic growth in India. However, fluctuations in market performance, investor behavior, and external economic factors create uncertainty for both individual and institutional investors. Despite the expansion of the Indian stock market, many investors lack adequate awareness and face challenges in making informed investment decisions. Additionally, macroeconomic variables such as inflation, interest rates, and policy changes significantly influence market movements. Therefore, it is necessary to examine the relationship between stock market performance and the Indian economy, as well as the issues faced by investors, to understand its overall impact and growth prospects.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- 1) To explore the structure and operation of the stock market in India.

- 2) To explore the importance of the stock market for economic development in India.
- 3) To explore the link between stock market performance and economic growth.
- 4) To access challenges facing the Indian stock market as well as its prospects.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

1. **Research Design:** The study is based on a descriptive research design to investigate knowledge of the stock market.
2. **Sources of Information**
 - Primary Data – Collected from public through questionnaires
 - Secondary Data – Collected from Newspaper, Internet sources and Journals.
3. **Sampling Method:** Convenience sampling method is used to collect responses from Public.
4. **Sample Size:** The study includes 61 respondents from various parts of the society.
5. **Data Collection Tool:** A structured questionnaire is used to gather information regarding stock market awareness.
6. **Tools Used for Data Analysis:**
 - One-Way ANOVA and Independent Sample T-Test
 - Tables and Graph
7. **Area of Study:** General Public.

DATA ANALYSIS

1. Analysis of demographic information like age, gender, and course of study.
2. Independent Sample T-Test for stock market awareness of the general public.
3. Study on Awareness of Stock Market among general public.
4. Study on Knowledge of Stock Market among general public .
5. Independent Sample T-Test for determining the Investment Behaviour.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. The study has shown that most respondents belong to the 21-30 years of age group, thus showing that youngsters are more interested in the stock market.
2. It was observed that males dominate stock market participation compared to females.
3. It has been shown in the study that most respondents have basic knowledge about the stock market and its functions.
4. It has been shown in the study that most respondents are aware of stock market investment opportunities in India.
5. It has been shown in the study that graduates form the largest group of respondents who are aware of stock market activities.

CONCLUSION

The study based on the stock market with reference to the Indian economy reveals that the awareness of stock market investments is slowly growing among individuals. Most of the respondents are aware of the basic knowledge of stock market activities and are aware of the importance of the stock market for economic growth. The study results reveal that age, gender, and educational qualifications of individuals are significant factors that influence their awareness of the stock market. From the study, it is evident that most of the respondents are interested in investing in the stock market for better returns, but some people are still hesitant due to the risk associated with it and a lack of proper knowledge. Education is one of the significant factors that influence the awareness of the stock market among individuals. The stock market is significantly contributing to the growth of the Indian economy by encouraging investments and savings. Financial literacy and proper guidance will help individuals make better investments and participate in the stock market.